

JOHN HECTOR – ONE OF THE FATHERS OF AMERICAN NOVELS

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Abstract: This article examines John Hector's famous works, and his lasting influence on the American novel. He explored the relationship between humans and nature, celebrating the virtues of agrarian life and portraying the American landscape as a source of both abundance and spiritual renewal in his books. Through closer analysis of his famous works, including "Letters from o'American Farmer" and "Sketches of Eighteenth Century America," John Hector's new perspectives, observations about America are explored.

Key words: John Hector St. John, American Novelist, "Letters from an American Farmer", Development of American Novels.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматриваются знаменитые произведения Джона Гектора и его длительное влияние на американский роман. В своих книгах он исследовал отношения между людьми и природой, прославляя достоинства аграрной жизни и изображая американский ландшафт как источник изобилия и духовного обновления. Путем более тщательного анализа его знаменитых произведений, в том числе «Письма американского фермера» и «Очерки Америки восемнадцатого века», наблюдений Джона Гектора, исследуются мнения об Америке.

Ключевые слова: Джон Гектор Сент-Джон, американский писатель, Письма американского фермера, Развитие американского писателя..

Izoh: Ushbu maqolada Jon Hektorning mashhur asarlari va uning Amerika romanchiligi rivojiga ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Jon Hektor o'zining asarlarida odamlar va tabiat o'rtasidagi munosabatlar agrar hayotning afzalliklarini tadqiq qilgan. Hamda Amerika landshaftini ham mo'l-ko'llik ramzi, ham ma'naviy yangilanish manbai sifatida tasvirlagan. Uning mashhur asarlari, jumladan, "Amerikalik fermerdan maktublar" va "O'n sakkizinchi asr Amerikasi eskizlari"ni chuqurroq tahlil qilish orqali Jon Hektorning Amerika haqidagi yangicha qarashlari, mulohazalari o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Jon Hektor Sent-Jon, Amerika romanchiligi, „Amerikalik fermerdan maktublar“, Amerika romanchiligi taraqqiyoti.

American novels reflect the cultural and spiritual life, internal mental state and outlook on life of Americans. This genre has developed under the influence of many factors throughout history. Technological progress, social and cultural changes, economic growth and political changes are obvious examples of these factors. The development of novel writing in America is associated with the names of writers and statesmen such as Benjamin Franklin and his contemporaries Thomas Jefferson, Thomas Paine, John Adams [1,196]. Moreover, John Hector St. John has an incomparable role in this development. John Hector St. John Crèvecoeur is widely recognized as one of the founding fathers of the American novel. His literary contribution not only paved the way for a unique American literary voice, but also created a new genre that will captivate

readers for generations. Born in the late 18th century, St. John's life experiences and careful observations of human nature shaped his writings and made him a prominent figure in American literature.

If we look at the literary legacy of John Hector, he is best known for his epistolary novel "Letters from an American Farmer," which was published in 1782. This collection of essays is considered one of the most significant literary contributions to early American literature and offers thought-provoking insights into the cultural, social, and geographical landscape of the United States during the late 18th century. This novel is composed of a series of fictional letters written by an American farmer named James, in which he details his experiences and observations while living in the American colonies. Through these letters, Crèvecoeur explored the diverse facets of American life, including the interactions among different ethnic and cultural groups, rural life and farming activities in early America, the unique characteristics of the American landscape, the spirit of entrepreneurship and innovation, and the emerging American identity. Through this work, John Hector shows the important function of American novels, "the American novel has usually seemed content to explore, rather than to appropriate and civilize, the remarkable and in some ways unexampled territories of life in the New World and to reflect its anomalies and dilemmas. It has not wanted to build an imperium but merely to discover a new place and a new state of American". [2, 43] The letters discuss topics such as the importance of agriculture, natural resources, and the social structure of the local population and colonies. In his novel Letters from an American Farmer, John Hector praises agrarian life by using the character of Farmer James, who comes not from Orange County, New York, but from a farm near Carlisle, Pennsylvania. Through James, John Hector embodies the quintessential individual navigating the challenges and promises of the American landscape. James represents the intersecting identities and aspirations of the diverse American population, offering a lens through which the reader can contemplate the multifaceted nature of the early American experience. St. John notes that a century ago, the vast fields and prosperous houses here were a whole wilderness. However, he admits that there have been many positive changes by the hand of mankind. At the same time, he mentions the brutality of slavery in the southern states and the lawlessness of the western frontier: " Even under those mild climates which seem to breathe peace and happiness, the poison of slavery, the fury of despotism, and the rage of superstition are all combined against man!" [3, 239]. Crèvecoeur's eloquent and vivid prose not only captured the physical beauty of the American land but also delved into the aspirations, challenges, and cultural blending that defined the early American experience. His writing style, which combined elements of fiction, autobiography, and social commentary, offered a nuanced and multifaceted portrayal of American society during a crucial period of its formation. The impact of "Letters from an American Farmer" extended beyond its immediate reception, influencing subsequent generations of American writers and thinkers. Crèvecoeur's contemplations on the nature of American identity and the promise of the New World have contributed to a robust and enduring discourse on the American Dream, immigration, and the evolving cultural tapestry of the United States.

Additionally, one of John Hector's notable works is Sketches of Eighteenth Century American, which contains thoughts on deforestation and drought. He attributed the drought in certain regions to the draining of seams and destruction of the forests. Many brooks fed by the swamps had dried up. "Our ancient woods kept the Earth moist and damp, and the Sun could evaporate

none of the waters contained under the shades”. [5, 107] He also noticed that in these regions the water table was sinking and as a consequence wells had to be dug deeper than formerly in order to find water. He wasn’t worried about the extent of soil erosion just yet but of course that would be consequence of the loss of the compass formed by decaying leaves, which had taken centuries to accumulate, and could be destroyed in one generation. According to an early settler in Crèvecoeur’s *Journey into Northern Pennsylvania and the State of New York*: “The second generation will regret bitterly that their fathers destroyed so much”. [6, 37] Crèvecoeur could be considered the first American ecologist, even though the term ecology had not yet been used at that time.

Conclusion

John Hector is still regarded as a significant character in American literature, having had a profound impact on the growth of the novel genre as well as the country’s overall literary scene. His writings focus on exploring the core American values of freedom, equality, and opportunity for all individuals, regardless of social status or background. His description of the “American Dream” as a country where people could create a better life for themselves captured the imagination of many readers at the time and continues to influence modern interpretations. The fact that St. John’s works sought to reflect the essence of America in his novels had a significant impact on subsequent generations of American writers. Authors such as James Fenimore Cooper and Mark Twain were inspired by his approach to stories and themes related to national identity, cultural diversity, and the American experience. In general, John Hector St. John’s “*Letters from an American Farmer*” and American values, his deep exploration of cultural diversity and rural life earned him an important place among the founding fathers of the American novel. John Hector’s works have a place in American literature to this day due to his contribution to the development of American literature and the significant influence on the works of modern writers.

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